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PEDAGOGICAL DESCRIPTION OF THE CONCEPTS OF “COMMUNICABILITY” AND “COMMUNICATIVE ABILITY”

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Abstract: The article mainly discusses the issues of the widespread use of communicative and communicative competence in language teaching, considering students as the main subjects of the educational process, developing students' speech culture through their understanding and thorough study of language means, and the widespread application of cognitive approaches in the teaching process.

Key words: communicative-cognitive methodology, communicative competence, speech culture, communicative activity, communicative attitudes, cognitive approach, criteria, behavioral approach.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada, asosan, til o'qitishda kommunikativ va kommunikativ qobiliyatni keng qo'llash, o'quvchilarni ta'lim jarayonining asosiy sub'ekti sifatida ko'rib chiqish, ularni tushunish va til ifodalash vositalarini puxta o'rganish orqali o'quvchilarning nutq madaniyatini rivojlantirish hamda o'qitish jarayonida kognitiv yondashuvlarni keng tatbiq etish masalalari muhokama qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: kommunikativ-kognitiv metodologiya, kommunikativ kompetensiya, nutq madaniyati, kommunikativ faoliyat, kommunikativ munosabatlar, kognitiv yondashuv, mezonlar, xulq-atvor yondashuvi.

Аннотация: В статье в основном рассматривается широкое использование коммуникативных и коммуникативных умений в обучении языку, рассмотрение учащихся как основных субъектов образовательного процесса, развитие речевой культуры учащихся посредством тщательного изучения их понимания и языковых средств выражения, а также широкое применение когнитивных подходов в процессе обучения.

Ключевые слова: коммуникативно-когнитивная методика, коммуникативная компетентность, культура речи, коммуникативная деятельность, коммуникативные отношения, когнитивный подход, критерии, поведенческий подход.

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, the terms “communicative” and “communicative ability” are widely used not only in linguistics but also in other fields of science. We believe that the linguistic meaning of the word “communicative” is “relationship” or “perception through language.” We rely on such a definition because we believe that the systematic improvement of each student's speech culture is directly related to the development of educational and communicative speech actions.

In recent years, UNESCO has put forward the idea of expanding the use of information and communication technologies in education and has made it one of the main priorities of its activities.

The concept of “communicative” dates back to the 1960s and began to be widely used in the study of Kazakh and Uzbek linguistics.

In a number of sources, this term is interpreted differently. For example, communication is the process of exchanging information in various interpersonal relationships between people. The main elements that help control or organize the communicative act are: source or information (the producer and transmitter/speaker of the text), recipient/receiver (the person to whom the information is intended and who expects a certain attitude), text (meaningful information encoded by certain signs or elements), channel (the means of transmitting information through which the text is transmitted from the main source to the receiver), result (the recipient's attitude to the information received), feedback (information about the recipient's attitude, perceived by the source and evaluated in terms of its correlation with their observations).

Communicative competence refers to the concept of communication, pedagogical, and technical skills and abilities. Communicative activity is the purposeful relationship of teachers and students with other teachers, team members, and parents.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Researcher N.K. Akhmedova emphasizes that communicativeness is a professional and personal approach, highlighting the need for individuals to rely on human factors during the communication process, to explain educational goals to each team member, to motivate them to perform assigned tasks, and to maintain constant communication with team members.

The idea of teaching a language communicatively was proposed by English methodologists in the second half of the last century. In her scientific work, F.I. Ikromkhonova shows that data from cognitive psychology were primarily used in the context of American methods of teaching foreign languages. The term communicative is often used interchangeably with communicative competence. Most scholars define communicative competence as a system of internal capabilities necessary for acquiring deep knowledge of communication. In their opinion, communicative competence is the ability to initiate, interact, and think. The competence aligned with the state educational standard of the secondary education system is defined as the ability to apply existing knowledge, skills, and qualifications in everyday social activities.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Communicative competence plays a crucial role in language teaching and holds great significance. In efforts to improve the quality of education in native and state languages, special attention is given to students' communicative competence – that is, their ability to independently compare knowledge gained in the native language with that in the state language, particularly in Uzbek-medium schools. It is essential to create favorable communicative conditions for analyzing both languages during practical classes.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Encouraging students to think freely and independently and to express their opinions through various communicative actions is not, in itself, a solution to the problem. In recent years, great importance has been attached to communicative competence in language teaching. The following linguodidactic issues are considered essential in developing students' communicative and cognitive abilities:

- Not the transmission of knowledge, but independent learning and self-directed study;
- In the multinational Republic of Uzbekistan, the state language serves as a means of communication;
- Creating favorable communicative and cognitive conditions and developing speech skills that enable students to communicate freely in both languages;
- Increasing students' interest in learning the language;
- Creating speech contexts related to the market economy, national identity, spiritual and educational matters, and public life amid the continuous development of society;
- Instilling in students a sense of patriotism and appreciation for independence by familiarizing them with the ethnic and cultural identities of both the Uzbek and English peoples.

Modern education today sets an important task: transforming students from passive recipients who merely repeat the teacher's thoughts during lessons into active participants with well-developed communicative and cognitive abilities—students who think freely and independently and are eager to explore the world. The memorization of theoretical knowledge by students is not an indicator of deep understanding. As A. Albetkova noted, "Knowledge of theory is not reflected in students' ability to recite rules by heart, but rather in their ability to perceive the rule and apply it in speech, especially after reading a novel."

CONCLUSION

The tasks assigned to human speech activity are extensive. One of its key functions is communicativeness, which plays a vital role in establishing communication, relationships, and mutual understanding between people. Through such communicative actions, individuals share necessary information and exchange thoughts. In this process, communicators develop a culture of speech.

Speech culture educates young people in the nuances of communication—for example: how to greet others in daily life, whom to talk to, what to say, when and where to say it, and how to articulate various processes appropriately.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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